

A comparative analysis of a perceptual hearing loss assessment dataset and the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health Core Sets for Hearing Loss

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Abstract

Objective: Traditional hearing assessments often overlook key aspects of hearing loss and its impact on daily life. Applying the World Health Organization's International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) Core Sets for Hearing Loss (CSHL), this study analyses a new dataset consisting of diverse audiological and functional measures. The aim is to evaluate the dataset's content according to the ICF framework to determine its potential for supporting patient-centered hearing loss intervention and rehabilitation. **Design:** The dataset includes results from otoscopy, pure-tone audiometry, a self-reported hearing and functioning questionnaire (HEAR-COMMAND Tool), speech intelligibility tests (Göttinger Sentence Test, GöSA and Oldenburger Sentence Test, OLSA), listening effort evaluation (Adaptive Categorical Listening Effort Scaling, ACALES), loudness perception assessments (Loudness Validation Method, LVM, and Adaptive Categorical Loudness Scaling), a multi-talker conversation task (Concurrent Oldenburger Sentence Test, CCOLSA), coupler measurements, in-situ recordings, tone-in-noise perception thresholds, and the Dialogue Picture Task (DIAPIX). Using the ICF linking rules, all measures, performed on 76 participants, were systematically mapped to ICF categories. **Results:** For the brief CSHL, the dataset addressed 92.5% of the categories. Only two categories, related to brain and inner ear structures, were missing. For the comprehensive CSHL, the dataset addressed 50.4% of the categories. This included 81.8% of Body Functions, 40% of Body Structures, 59.5% of Activities and Participation, and 29.1% of Environmental Factors. **Conclusion:** The dataset covered half of the categories in the comprehensive CSHL, which reflects its strong validity. By integrating diverse audiological and functional assessments, it enables the creation of detailed profiles of an individual's HL that effectively reveal critical HL-related factors, needs, limitations, and daily challenges. Such ecologically valid, individualized profiles can support hearing aid technology development and enhance effectiveness in complex listening environments. As a result, this dataset can ultimately improve rehabilitation outcomes, user satisfaction, and quality of life.

1 Introduction

Hearing Loss (HL) is one of the most common disabilities worldwide. Early diagnosis and intervention are therefore a clinically relevant focus of audiology research (Cunningham & Tucci, 2017; WHO 2018; Chadha et al., 2021). In 2019, an estimated 1.57 billion people were affected by HL (Haile et al., 2021), which shows the importance of improving assessment methods. Current HL clinical assessments for adults typically include gathering medical history, evaluating ear structure, and conducting pure-tone and speech audiometry. Although these measurements provide useful information about an individual's HL, they often fail to address a wide range of factors related to the causes and consequences of HL. Furthermore, such measurements are typically performed in controlled laboratory settings and do not reflect the real-life consequences of HL, particularly the ability to function in complex listening environments. In other words, these measurements are not ecologically valid and do not fully reflect the challenges individuals experience in their daily lives.

For example, as opposed to pure-tone audiometry, where listening thresholds are measured using a single tone in a quiet environment, in real-life environments an individual must detect sounds across a wide range of frequencies and in the presence of multiple distracting sounds (auditory maskers). As a result, the outcome of pure-tone audiometry alone does not necessarily reflect the degree of hearing difficulty an individual faces in daily life. Another example of the limited ecological validity of common HL measures is the lack of assessment of communication and conversational abilities in everyday life, which becomes more severe in noisy environments. Furthermore, the impact of HL on non-audiological aspects such as social participation, cognitive functioning, and overall quality of life is often neglected in HL assessment. For instance, loneliness can result from limited communication caused by HL, which can further diminish an individual's quality of life. Several studies demonstrated relationships between HL and social isolation, cognitive decline, depression, and dementia (Rutherford et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2011, 2013; Deal et al., 2017; Barker et al., 2017; Kramer et al., 2002; Pronk et al., 2011; Sung et al., 2016; Mick et al., 2014).

Therefore, recent audiology research progressively focuses on enhancing the ecological validity of HL assessment methods to accurately predict the difficulties brought on by HL and to evaluate the effectiveness of hearing aids in overcoming such challenges. To identify all the aspects needed to be included in HL assessment, a universal reference is needed. The World Health Organization's International Classification of Functioning Disability and Health (ICF)

framework is a globally accepted standard that defines a bio-psycho-social model to relate a health condition to functioning, disability and contextual factors (WHO 2001, 2013).

According to the ICF framework, functioning and disability refer to Body Functions (BF), Body Structure (BS), and Activities and Participation (AP). Contextual factors refer to Environmental Factors (EF) and Personal Factors (PF). These domains are further divided into more detailed concepts in a hierarchical manner. For example, the BF domain includes eight chapters; chapter one: "Mental Functions" (b1); chapter two: "Sensory functions and pain" (b2); and so on. "Mental functions" (b1) itself is divided into global and specific mental functions. "Specific mental functions" divides into twelve categories, including "Attention Functions" (b140), "Perceptual Functions" (b156), and others. Finally, "Perceptual Functions" (b156) itself divides into eight subcategories, such as "Auditory Perception" (b1560) and "Visual Perception" (b1561) (WHO 2001, 2013).

The ICF Core Sets for Hearing Loss (CSHLs) are two collections of ICF categories that include the most crucial aspects (categories) related to HL. The "Brief" CSHL includes 27 and the "Comprehensive" CSHL includes 117 of the ICF categories (Danermark et al., (2010, 2013); Granberg (2015); Granberg et al., (2014a, 2014b, 2014c, 2014d). The complete list of the categories can be found in Danermark et al., (2013).

To integrate the ICF into clinical practice, a variety of measurements are required to address both audiological and non-audiological ICF categories within the CSHLs. Some ICF categories that are not addressed in current HL assessment procedures, such as "Temperament and personality functions" (b126), can be evaluated through self-report measures (questionnaires or interviews). Others can only be assessed by Hearing Healthcare Professionals (HHPs) via medical examinations and screenings, such as "Structure of brain" (s110). Finally, some categories, such as "Listening" (d115), can be assessed both through self-report measures and in clinical settings from different perspectives.

The measurements and outcomes included in HL assessments can be correlated with the ICF framework to compare the concepts covered in HL evaluation with the ICF CSHLs categories. This procedure is conducted according to the recommended ICF linking principles (Cieza et al., 2002, 2005; Granberg et al., 2014c). As a result, the degree to which an HL assessment method aligns with the ICF can be revealed, and any uncovered categories can be identified. Such linking procedures to the brief and comprehensive CSHL have been performed on multiple intake documents, questionnaires, and interviews used in audiology clinics and

Otology medical centres in the USA and the Netherlands. It was found that, overall, the comprehensive CSHL categories within the AP and EF domains were poorly covered in all records (van Leeuwen et al., 2017; Alfakir et al., 2019).

Similar to the aforementioned studies, clinical datasets and measurements can be linked to the ICF categories, as a common language, to assess their scope and inclusiveness. In a recent study (Afghah et al., 2023), the content and outcomes of an audiological diagnostics dataset in Germany were linked to the CSHLs. This dataset included results from interviews, pure-tone audiometry, speech intelligibility tests, and adaptive categorical loudness scaling measurements performed on 1316 participants. The linking procedure revealed that all these measurements combined addressed less than half (44%) of the most essential categories in the brief CSHL and only 18% of those in the comprehensive CSHL. Out of seventeen BF domain categories in the comprehensive CSHL, only six were addressed. Except for "Auditory Perception" (b1560), none of the categories within the "Mental functions" (b1) or "Voice and speech functions" (b3) chapters were covered.

The analysis showed that only 17% of the AP and 12% of the EF categories in the comprehensive CSHL were covered. Apart from three categories, "Health Professionals" (e355), "Health Services, Systems, and Policies" (e580), and "Arts and Culture" (d9202), the AP and EF chapters, which focus on the consequences of HL on an individual's social wellbeing, were not addressed. It was evident that additional measures needed to be included in the HL assessment to effectively address these missing factors. Due to the nature of these categories, it was concluded that their inclusion of many categories requires self-reporting. Therefore, a new questionnaire, the "HEAR-COMMAND Tool", was thereafter developed to inquire about the most critical missing categories within these chapters (Afghah et al., 2022, 2024; Alfakir et al., 2025a, 2025b). In addition, the common standard HL assessment methods, linked to categories such as "Hearing Functions" (b230), reflect clinical measurements results. However, the results of such measures may not fully align with an individual's hearing difficulties in daily life. For instance, the results of typical laboratory-based speech intelligibility tests may not represent the speech perception challenges in echoic environments such as churches. Therefore, to facilitate comparison between clinical test results and an individual's real-life experience, these categories were also included in the HEAR-COMMAND Tool. Applying this tool helps to define an individual's needs and limitations by incorporating both HHPs' and patients' perspectives (Afghah et al., 2022, 2024).

The objective of this study is to evaluate the alignment between ICF CSHLs and the content of a newly collected HL assessment dataset. The dataset contains the results of various measurements developed to support research on modelling unaided and aided speech intelligibility and listening effort in ecologically relevant settings. By linking the dataset content to the CSHLs categories, the extent to which these measurements address the essential aspects of HL assessment will be revealed. Therefore, it can be determined how well this dataset represents individuals' daily life experiences, as defined by the ICF framework.

The materials and methods section provides a description of the measurements and their corresponding outcomes, while the applications of the ICF linking rules and the inclusion of the categories are presented in the results section.

2 Materials and Methods

The measurements were performed in 2022 and the generated dataset containing the results of each measurement was structured and modelled in 2023 and 2024. The dataset includes the measurements results for 76 participants and was collected at the Hörzentrum Oldenburg gGmbH, Germany and accessible on Zenodo platform (Afghah et al., 2025a)¹. This section provides a summary of the measurements. For a detailed description and the measurements results, refer to Afghah et al., (2025b) and Gerken et al., (2025).

2.1 HEAR-COMMAND Tool

The HEAR-COMMAND Tool (HCT) was developed and validated through an international collaboration and is available in English, German, Arabic, and Korean (Afghah et al., 2022, 2024; Alfakir et al., 2025a, 2025b)². This tool was developed to incorporate both the brief and comprehensive CSLH categories, which are often missing in HL assessment, into rehabilitation and clinical practice. The tool focuses on functioning, social well-being, and communication and conversation ability. Among the 120 items (questions) of the tool, 90 items cover BF, AP, and EF domains and 30 address the PF domain and concepts not categorized within the ICF framework. The HCT responses are summarized into three scores: Hearing-related score, Speech perception score, and Non-hearing-related score, each on a scale from 0 to 10. The tool

¹ Accessible at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14864856>

² Accessible at <https://www.hz-ol.de/en/open-tools-for-science/hear-command-tool>

was provided to participants in a paper-pencil format and required approximately 15-20 minutes to complete.

2.2 Otoscopy

In the first session, an audiologist performed Otoscopy and evaluated the condition of the outer and middle ear including the tympanic membrane.

2.3 Pure-tone Audiometry

Air Conduction (AC) thresholds, Bone Conduction (BC) thresholds, and Uncomfortable Loudness levels (UCL) were measured during pure-tone audiometry. Based on the pure-tone average (PTA) of the better ear, calculated from AC thresholds at 0.5, 1, 2, and 4KHz, the degree of HL was determined. This included 20 participants with Normal Hearing (NH) and 56 participants with Hearing Impairment (HI) with mild to severe HL. The HI participants included those who did not use a hearing aid (N=25) and hearing aid users (N=31).

2.4 Binaural Broadband Loudness Scaling

The perceived loudness was measured via the Adaptive Categorical Loudness Scaling (ACALOS) method (Brand and Hohmann, 2002) with the task defined as grading the perceived loudness from "not heard" to "extremely loud" on an 11-point scale. The Loudness Scaling fitting method normalizes binaural broadband loudness perception by combining audiogram data with loudness perception measurements (Oetting et al., 2016, 2018). Narrowband loudness functions were calculated at 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, and 6 kHz (Suck et al., 2020; Zimmer et al., 2024) and binaural broadband loudness was evaluated by presenting two stimuli that were amplified with the narrowband gain through a headphone (a female speech-shaped noise (IFnoise, Holube et al., 2010) and a unified excitation noise (UEN17, Zwicker, 1961)). To calculate the required gains at 50, 65, and 80 dB SPL, binaural broadband loudness summation (Oetting et al., 2016), defined as the deviation of binaural broadband loudness function from normal-hearing reference values, along with the narrowband gains were used to normalize binaural broadband loudness perception (Oetting et al., 2018).

2.5 Loudness Validation Method

The Loudness Validation Method (LVM) is a recently developed approach for measuring deviations in loudness perception of HA users compared to a normal-hearing reference (Exter et al., 2024; Jansen et al., 2020). In this method, 60 natural signals, divided into twelve presentation categories, were presented in a free-field setting. These categories differed in both

frequency range and presentation level. The participant was required to rate the perceived loudness on a scale with eleven responses from "not heard" to "extremely loud". The responses were then compared to reference response ranges, derived from a group of NH individuals. As a result, loudness perception in each of the twelve presentation categories was compared to normal-hearing references and classified into one of six levels: much softer, slightly softer, normal, slightly louder, much louder, and extremely loud.

2.6 Tone in Noise Detection

The Tone-in-Noise detection measurement, introduced by Schädler et al. (2020), was developed to assess frequency-specific suprathreshold auditory limitations. Detection thresholds were measured at 0.5 and 2 kHz for both ears in the presence of background white noise, using an adaptive procedure based on Kaernbach (1990), which estimates the tone level corresponding to 75% correct responses.

2.7 Coupler Measurements

In this technical measurement, sound pressure levels of hearing aids were measured at input levels of 50, 65, and 80 dB SPL using an ear simulator and the International Speech Test Signal (ISTS) (Holube et al., 2010).

2.8 In-situ Recordings

During the ACALES and OLSA, in-ear recordings were obtained using tube probe microphones placed in each ear canal while participants wore their own hearing aids to allow for the objective verification of the test signals.

2.9 Speech Recognition of Unpredictable Sentences via Oldenburg Sentence Test

Speech intelligibility was evaluated using the Oldenburg Sentence test (OLSA) (Wagener and Brand, 2005, Wagener et al., 1999a, 1999b, 1999c) across six settings. In four settings, OLSA sentences were presented in simulated real-life scenarios using 24 loudspeakers without visual stimuli. These listening scenarios were created by employing the virtual scenes generated for hearing and audiology research (van de Par et al., 2022; Grimm et al., 2021; Schütze et al., 2021; Hladek & Seeber, 2022), simulating a pub, an underground station, and a living room with two different layouts (with different target and masker sound source positions). In the other two settings, common spatial presentations were applied, with OLSA sentences presented with

adaptive speech level (Brand and Kollmeier, 2002), from a 0° azimuth angle and the speech-shaped noise (Olnoise, Wagener and Brand, 2005, Wagener et al., 1999 a) once from 0° (S0N0 setting) and once from 90° (S0N90 setting) azimuth angles. For HA users, measurements were performed both with and without their own HA.

2.10 Speech Recognition of Everyday Sentences via Göttingen Sentence Test

To evaluate speech intelligibility, the Göttingen sentence test (GÖSA) with adaptive speech level (Kollmeier and Wesselkamp 1997; Brand and Kollmeier, 2002) was conducted through a free-field equalized headphone in the S0N90 setting, with the noise level set to 65 dB SPL. For HA users, GÖSA measurement was also performed with the HA in place in a free-field setting.

2.11 Concurrent Oldenburg Sentence Test

The Concurrent Oldenburg Sentence Test (CCOLSA) was developed to measure speech recognition in simulated complex conversational scenarios involving three virtual talkers with partly overlapping speech alongside a diffuse cafeteria noise (Heeren et al., 2022, 2023). The three talkers presented OLSA sentences through loudspeakers positioned at -60°, 0°, and 60° azimuthal angles. Participants were required to perform tasks that demanded both hearing function and high cognitive load, particularly attention. The assigned tasks were defined as follows: 1. Detect the word "Kerstin" spoken by any of the talkers in their sentences and turn towards that talker. 2. Repeat the last words of all sentences from that talker following the "Kerstin" sentence until another talker spoke a sentence with "Kerstin", which indicates a target talker change.

2.12 Adaptive Categorical Listening Effort Scaling

The Adaptive Categorical Listening Effort Scaling (ACALES) measurement was conducted to assess listening effort (Krueger et al., 2017). Participants were instructed to rate the listening effort required to understand three consecutive OLSA sentences on a 13-level scale from "no effort" to "extreme effort". This measurement was performed in the same four virtual scenes as well as in S0N0 and S0N90 settings.

2.13 Dialogue Picture Task (DIAPIX) Measurements

The DIAPIX picture material (Baker & Hazan, 2011) was used in a German-translated version to elicit spontaneous speech between two participants. In each trial, each participant was provided with one of the two versions of an image which differed in twelve details. The task was to identify the differences between the image pair through communication between the two

participants who could only see their own image version. In such conversation tasks, the measurement outcome can be rated using various approaches, such as a self-reported survey that asks the participant to rate the conversation success (Nicoras et al., 2025) or by counting the number of differences correctly identified, both performed in this experiment. The maximum duration for the task was three minutes, and it was performed in three acoustic conditions: in quiet and in a restaurant background noise scene at overall presentation levels of 50 or 70 dB from a horizontal array of 16 loudspeakers. For more details of the procedure, see Schütze et al., 2020.

3 Results

In this section, the ICF linking outcomes for each measurement are reviewed. According to rule 12 of the ICF linking recommendations for audiological data (Granberg et al., 2014b), both the aim and procedure of each measurement were linked to the relevant ICF categories.

3.1 HEAR-COMMAND Tool

The details of the HCT ICF category linking are provided in the HCT development paper, Table 3 (Afghah et al., 2022). As this tool is originally an ICF-based questionnaire, its ninety items cover a substantial portion of the categories in both CSHLs. This includes 85% of the brief and 44% of the comprehensive CSHL categories. Apart from the BS domain, all the categories of the brief CSHL are covered by the tool. Overall, among the categories of comprehensive CSHL, 73% of BF, 55% of AP, and 27% of EF domains are covered. In this dataset, most of the categories addressed by the HCT, and not by any other methodology, are within the AP and EF domains, including "Domestic life" (AP, chapter d6), "Interpersonal interactions and relationships" (AP, chapter d7), "Major life areas" (AP, chapter d8), "Community, social and civil life" (AP, chapter d9), "Support and relationships" (EF, chapter e3), "Attitudes" (EF, chapter e4), and "Services, systems, and policies" (EF, chapter e5).

3.2 Otoscopy

Otoscopy was linked to the "Structure of external ear" (s240) and "Structure of middle ear" (s250), making it the only methodology in this dataset that addresses the BS domain categories.

3.3 Listening-based measurements

In this section, the linking results of the nine listening-based measurements, including GÖSA, OLSA, ACALES, TIN, LVM, PTA, CCOLSA, DIAPIX, and Binaural Broadband Loudness Scaling via ACALOS measurement, are given. To avoid redundancy, the linking outcomes of the most addressed categories are first presented collectively, based on their shared concept. Next, the remaining uniquely addressed categories are provided.

3.3.1 Detection of Sound in general

A) All nine measurements: Participants were assigned to a variety of tasks that demand mental functions needed to sense the presence of sound and actively and intentionally detect acoustic and auditory stimuli in the corresponding measurement environment. Therefore, these measurements were linked to "Sound detection" (b2300), "Auditory perception" (b1560), and "Sound intensity" (e2500).

B) ACALOS, LVM, TIN, and PTA: These measurements which require intentional listening to non-speech stimuli (Granberg et al., 2014b), were further linked to "Listening" (d115).

3.3.2 Detection of Sound in noise

A) GÖSA, OLSA, ACALES, CCOLSA, and DIAPIX: In these measurements, the target sounds were accompanied by different types of distracting sounds, including speech and background noise. Furthermore, they simulated real-life listening by creating speech-in-noise conditions that reflected environmental barriers and made sound perception challenging. Therefore, they were linked to "Speech discrimination" (b2304) and "Sound quality" (e2501).

B) TIN: In this measurement, a pure tone had to be segregated from background noise. Therefore, this was linked to "Sound discrimination" (b2301) and "Sound quality" (e2501).

C) OLSA, ACALES, CCOLSA, and DIAPIX: In DIAPIX and CCOLSA, the sound detection task was assigned while restaurant or cafeteria noise was presented. In OLSA and ACALES, an underground station and a pub were simulated. Although these measurements were not physically performed in these places, they simulated the noise created by the structure, design, and acoustic features of real environments and the barriers or facilitators present in such places. Therefore, following Granberg et al. (2014b) Rule 7, they were linked to "Design, construction and building products and technology of buildings for public use" (e150).

D) OLSA and ACALES: One of the three auditory virtual scenes in OLSA and ACALES was a living room, which was presented with different combinations of natural home background sounds such as a dishwasher and other people speaking at home. Therefore, these measurements

were linked to “Design, construction and building products and technology of buildings for private use” (e155).

3.3.3 Localization and Lateralization of sound

GÖSA, OLSA, ACALES, CCOLSA, and DIAPIX: The sounds in the OLSA, ACALES, and DIAPIX were presented from loudspeaker arrays positioned at different horizontal angles, using 24, 24, and 16 speakers, respectively. Furthermore, in the CCOLSA, sounds were presented from three horizontal angles (-60°, 0°, 60°) and in the GÖSA-S0N90 setting from two angles (0°, 90°). Therefore, due to the necessity of localizing the sound source and relative physical positioning of participants and loudspeakers, these measurements were linked to "Localisation of sound source" (b2302) and "Lateralization of sound" (b2303).

3.3.4 Voice functions

GÖSA, OLSA, CCOLSA, and DIAPIX: In CCOLSA, participants had to repeat the words following by the word "Kerstin". In OLSA and GÖSA, participants repeated the detected words from the test sentences verbally. In DIAPIX, participants actively talked to a partner, which required the production of words and sentences. These tasks highly involved voice and speech functions; therefore, these measurements were linked to the following ICF categories.

- "Production of voice" (b3100) and "Quality of voice" (b3101): Two subcategories of "Voice functions" (b310).
- "Articulation functions" (b320).
- "Fluency of speech" (b3300), "Rhythm of speech" (b3301), "Speed of speech" (b3302), and "Melody of speech" (b3303): Four subcategories of "Fluency and rhythm of speech functions" (b330).

3.3.5 Focusing and attention

A) All nine measurements: In these measurements, active sound detection and intentional listening directly involved cognitive processes and concentration ability. Performing these tasks was linked to the relative subcategories of "Attention functions" (b140) and "Focusing attention" (d160). This is because, during the measurements, the participant had to remain concentrated throughout the test duration, linked to "Sustaining attention" (b1400), shift focus between different stimuli and concentrate again across different test conditions, linked to "Shifting attention" (b1401), and notice changes in the quality and intensity of sounds, linked to "Focusing attention on the environment" (d1601). Although all nine measurements were

linked to these categories, the cognitive demand level varied among them, with the highest needed in CCOLSA and DIAPIX due to the requirements to perform complex multimodal tasks.

B) GÖSA, OLSA, ACALES, CCOLSA, DIAPIX, and TIN: These measurements were further linked to "Dividing attention" (b1402), as the sound and background noise had to be detected separately.

3.3.6 Memory functions

GÖSA, OLSA, CCOLSA, and DIAPIX: In the DIAPX measurement, participants were required to explain detected visual features to their partner. In the CCOLSA, they had to repeat the words presented after the word "Kerstin". In GÖSA and OLSA, participants were required to remember and repeat the detected words of the presented sentences. Therefore, in all these measurements, recalling new information was a fundamental requirement for performing the assigned tasks. As a result, these measurements were linked to "Short-term memory" (b1440) that is a subcategory of "Memory functions" (b144).

3.3.7 Complex tasks

DIAPIX and CCOLSA: To perform the tasks in DIAPIX, participants had to focus on both visual and auditory cues, integrate them, and eventually describe the detected features in the image. In CCOLSA, participants had to detect a word ("Kerstin"), turn towards the sound source, detect the following words, and repeat them. In both measurements, completing the assigned complex tasks required a high cognitive load. Therefore, performing these tasks was linked to the following categories.

- "Acquiring complex skills" (d1551): A subcategory of "Acquiring skills" (d155).
- "Problem Solving" (b1646): A subcategory of "Higher-level cognitive functions" (b164).
- "Solving complex problems" (d1751): A subcategory of "Solving Problems" (d175).
- "Completing multiple tasks" (d2201): A subcategory of "Undertaking multiple tasks" (d220).

In DIAPIX participants actively engaged in a conversation task. In CCOLSA, although conversation partners were virtual, pre-recorded OLSA sentences played through loudspeakers simulated a realistic multi-talker conversational scenario. Identifying the appropriate onset (starting time), continuing, and ending the stream of words was similar to what participants

would experience in real-world listening situations. Therefore, both measurements were linked to three subcategories of "Conversation" (d350): "Starting a conversation" (d3500), "Sustaining a conversation" (d3501), and "Ending a conversation" (d3502).

3.3.8 Unique categories of DIAPIX

Since the DIAPIX task demanded making meaningful sentences, understanding the meaning of the partner's sentences, conversing and discussing the objects in the images with the participant, it was also linked to the following categories.

- "Sharing attention (b1403)": A subcategory of "Attention functions" (b140).
- "Reception of spoken language" (b16700): A subcategory of "Reception of Language" (b1670), which itself is a subcategory of "Mental functions of language" (b167).
- "Expression of spoken language" (b16710): A subcategory of "Expression of Language" (b1671), which itself is a subcategory of "Mental functions of language" (b167).
- "Focusing attention on the person" (d1600): A subcategory of "Focusing attention" (d160).
- "Communicating with - receiving - simple spoken messages" (d3100): A subcategory of "Communicating with - receiving - spoken messages" (d310).
- "Producing complex spoken messages" (d3302): A subcategory of "Speaking" (d330).
- "Conversing with one person" (d3503): A subcategory of "Conversation" (d350).
- "Discussion with one person" (d3550): A subcategory of "Discussion" (d355).
- "Relating with strangers" (d730).

As performing the task in DIAPIX measurement required seeing and identifying the shape, colour, and unique features of objects in the image, it was also linked to the following categories: "Visual perception" (b1561), "Watching" (d110), "Light" (e240), and three subcategories of "Quality of vision" (b2102): "Light sensitivity" (b21020), "Colour vision" (b21021), and "Contrast sensitivity" (b21022).

3.3.9 Unique categories of CCOLSA

The CCOLSA measurement setup simulated a multi-talker conversation scenario. Consequently, participation and recognition of words spoken by three virtual speakers were linked to "Conversing with many people" (d3504), a subcategory of "Conversation" (d350). Repeating single words (those heard after the word "Kerstin") was linked to a subcategory of "Speaking" (d330): "Producing meaningful sounds" (d3300). Since the OLSA sentences used

in CCOLSA did not provide auditory cues based on understanding the meaning of words or the sentence as a whole, this measurement was not linked to ICF codes that address speech comprehension. This is because categories such as "Producing simple spoken messages" (d3301), "Reception of spoken language" (b16700), or "Communicating with - receiving - simple spoken messages" (d3100) imply decoding the meaning of speech, which did not apply to the CCOLSA task.

3.4 Coupler measurements and in-situ recordings

Coupler measurements and in-situ recordings performed during OLSA and ACALES measurements were linked to "Sound intensity" (e2500) and "Sound quality" (e2501) as they verify the level and quality of the signals amplified and presented to the participant. They were both further linked to "Assistive products and technology for communication (e1251)" which is a subcategory of "Products and technology for communication" (e125).

3.5 Overall covered ICF categories

Table 1 shows the results of the ICF-linking procedure to the comprehensive CSHL categories for each measurement. In several cases, the measurements were linked to third or fourth-level categories that are represented in one or both Core Sets by their higher-level categories. The categories "Taste function" (b250), "Smell function" (b255), and "Sleep functions" (b134) are included in the HCT but are not covered in either the brief or comprehensive CSHL.

Insert table 1 here.

Table 2 presents the number of categories addressed by each measurement across both CSHLs. Overall, the dataset addresses 92.5% of the categories in the brief CSHL with the remaining 7.5% corresponding to two missing BS domain categories; "Structure of brain" (s110) and "Structure of inner ear" (s260). All the categories in BF, AP, and EF domains in the brief CSHL were fully covered. Furthermore, the dataset covered 50.4% of the categories in the comprehensive CSHL including 81.8% of the BF, 40% of the BS, 59.5% of the AP, and 29.1% of the EF domain categories.

Insert table 2 here.

3.6 Missing ICF Categories of Core Sets for Hearing Loss

Table 3 shows the comprehensive CSHL categories not addressed in the dataset, organized into seven groups, with the first four groups combining AP and EF categories. Group 1 includes 22

categories corresponding to broad general life dimensions such as economic life, politics, policies, culture, religion, human rights, climate, and domestic life. Group 2 includes four categories focused on unique concepts such as intimate relationships and domesticated animals. Group 3 includes four categories related to mobility and transportation. Group 4 consists of seven categories related to work preparation, training, learning, and developing skills.

Group 5 corresponds to 14 categories from the EF domain under "Support and relationships" (chapter e3) and "Attitudes" (chapter e4). These categories refer to an individual's relationship and interaction with people with whom they have limited daily contact such as people in position of authority or strangers. Group 6 consists of four missing BF domain categories, including three categories of "Mental functions" (chapter b1) - "Intellectual functions", "Energy level", and "Motivation"- as well as "Vestibular functions" (b235). Group 7 contains three missing BS domain categories: "Structure of brain" (s110), "Structure of inner ear" (s260), and "Structure of head and neck region" (s710).

Insert table 3 here.

3.7 Personal Factors and content not covered by the ICF

The first 30 items in the HCT address a wide range of PF as well as concepts not covered by the ICF, such as time aspects, health condition status, and hearing aid usage. In summary, these items inquire about gender, age, marital status, living situation, occupation, educational background, loud noise exposure history, family history of HL, past and current general and hearing health status (Afghah et al., 2022).

4 Discussion

This dataset was developed to be used for modelling the impact of hearing impairment and the benefits of hearing aids. A variety of measurements were included to ensure that the resulting model would address a broad range of factors interacting with HL and therefore is representative of individuals' daily life experiences. The measurements included in the dataset were linked to the ICF categories of core sets for hearing loss. The outcome of the linking procedure allowed to define the dataset's scope in terms of inclusion of the most important aspects of HL and its consequences on daily functioning. The results showed that 92.5% of the categories in the brief CSHL and 50.4% of those in the comprehensive CSHL were addressed within this dataset.

Based on the number of categories addressed by each measurement (as shown in Table 2), it can be observed that pure-tone audiometry covers only 14.8% of the brief and 5.2% of the comprehensive CSHL categories, even though PTA is traditionally considered a core measure for HL. This finding aligns with revised guidelines and recommendations to include additional assessment methods, particularly self-report measures, in HL evaluations (de Gruy et al., 2023; NGC 2018).

Excluding the HEAR-COMMAND Tool, an ICF-based self-assessment instrument, highlights the substantial portion of categories that remain uncovered. This emphasizes that it is essential to incorporate self-assessment tools to broadly evaluate HL and its consequences in daily life, as recommended by the ICF framework.

4.2 Dataset strengths and inclusions

4.2.1 Comprehensive Coverage of ICF Categories

The coverage of half of the categories in the comprehensive CSHL allows researchers to identify and evaluate the needs and limitations associated with HL on a large scale, based on an internationally accepted standard. This means, conducting these measurements facilitates the creation of an "ICF-based profile", which broadly reflects the causes and impacts of HL on an individual's life. Addressing these personalized aspects enables the improvement in HA perceptual models and potentially improves HAs performance to closely align with the specific needs identified in daily life and improve patient satisfaction with the HA.

The highest number of ICF categories in this dataset are addressed by the HEAR-COMMAND Tool. This is because, as previously stated, this tool was developed to address ICF categories initially found missing in another evaluated dataset (Afghah et al., 2023), and in multiple intake documentation investigated in other studies (van Leeuwen et al., 2017, Alfakir et al., 2019). One could argue that a large number of ICF categories addressed in this dataset are only covered by the HCT and no other measurement. However, this result is expected, as self-report is usually the only measure that can be used to evaluate many of these uniquely addressed categories. For some of these categories, laboratory-based measurements either have not been developed to date or it may not be possible to create tests that address them.

4.2.2 Environmental factors inclusion

Apart from "Sound intensity" (e2500) and "Sound quality" (e2501), most HL hearing assessment methods do not commonly address other EF domain categories. With the inclusion of the HCT in this dataset, all essential EF categories, gathered in the brief CSHL, are targeted.

The impacts of building construction and design on an individual's mobility limitations are taken into account in the subcategories of "Design, construction and building products and technology of buildings for public use" (e150). The physical features addressed include entering and exiting buildings (e1500), gaining access to facilities inside buildings (e1501), way finding, path routing and designation of locations in buildings (e1502), and physical safety of persons (e1503). However, the impacts of the acoustic features and architecture of buildings on the communication abilities of individuals are not included in these subcategories, despite having a large impact, particularly for hearing impaired individuals. The application of sound-absorbing materials can reduce sound reflections from surfaces, consequently decreasing the reverberation of sound in the environment. This would result in a higher speech intelligibility and effectiveness of hearing aids in noisy environments. It has been demonstrated that the classroom acoustics have a direct impact on speech intelligibility, social behaviour, and the overall performance of students (Shield & Dockrell 2003; Bradley & Sato, 2008; Tiesler et al., 2015).

In this dataset, such effects are represented through the application of different virtual scenes in speech intelligibility and listening effort measurements. Conducting measurements in simulated buildings (underground station, pub, and living room) can reflect the acoustical features of those environments and allow for comparison of an individual's performance across different listening conditions.

4.2.3 Cognitive load assessment

Multiple measurements were linked to third and fourth-level categories within the first chapters of the BF and AP domains, "Mental functions" and "Learning and applying knowledge", respectively. This includes both global and specific mental functions, as well as purposeful sensory experiences, basic learning, and applying knowledge. The inclusion of cognitive load assessment in HL evaluation at a detailed level results in a holistic approach to identify the factors that contribute to an individual's communication and conversation abilities, beyond hearing functions. Such measurements are not typically included in common HL hearing assessment methods.

4.2.4 Conversation ability assessment

In typical HL assessment procedures, only one side of the conversation task which is passive listening to what is told (played through headphones or loudspeakers in laboratory settings) is commonly evaluated. However, conversation is a two-sided activity that involves both listening and speaking. In this dataset, by combining the outcome of HCT, CCOLSA, and DIAPIX, all specified subcategories of the category "Conversation" (d350) were addressed.

4.2.5 Self-assessment vs. Listening-based measurements

The possibility of cross-methodology analysis becomes particularly important when comparing self-reported difficulties (measured here using the HCT) with laboratory-based measurements. Case in point, the concept of communication (AP, chapter d3) is well-represented in the dataset. All relevant ICF categories from this chapter included in the comprehensive CSHL were addressed. These categories were all covered in the HCT, which provides a broad self-report overview of the communication limitations. Additionally, conversational and discussion abilities were evaluated using the CCOLSA and DIAPIX measurements. This allows for a direct comparison between an individual's self-reported communication challenges and the results of laboratory-based evaluations. Consequently, matches and mismatches between self-assessment and clinical assessment could be identified.

Furthermore, the HCT includes multiple questions that assess difficulties experienced when hearing in noisy environments. An individual's responses to these items can be compared with outcomes from measurements involving sound or, more specifically, speech stimuli presented in the presence of interfering sounds. Moreover, by comparing the HCT speech perception score with the Speech Reception Threshold values measured in OLSA or GÖSA, a direct comparison can be established between self-reported speech comprehension and laboratory-measured speech intelligibility (Gerken et al., 2025).

4.2.6 Real-life simulations

HL assessment is commonly conducted in an acoustically treated laboratory where reverberation is minimized. These controlled environments do not represent real-life listening scenarios, which often include other competing sounds (speech and/or non-speech). In this dataset, three virtual scenes were used to evaluate listening effort (in ACALES) and speech intelligibility (in OLSA) within real-life simulated scenes, enhancing the ecological validity of the HL assessment compared to typical measurements.

4.3 Dataset limitations and exclusions

The majority of the AP and EF domains missing categories (groups 1 to 5) cannot be effectively examined in a laboratory setting. Similar concepts such as the relationship with immediate family members and friends is covered in HCT, however since the tool contains 120 items, such less critical categories were excluded to shorten the time needed to complete the questionnaire and avoid user fatigue. The inclusion of such categories in HL evaluation could be feasible through developing an additional questionnaire or by conducting an interview. However, addressing these 55 missing categories would require a large number of questions, resulting a longer visiting appointment. Alternatively, similar to the HCT, such questionnaire could be provided to patients to complete at home prior to the appointment.

To incorporate some of the missing BF and BS categories (groups 6 and 7), medical imaging techniques such as MRI or CT scans to address "Structure of brain" (s110) and "Structure of inner ear" (s260), diagnostic examinations such as Vestibular Function Testing (VFTs) to cover "Vestibular functions" (b235), and motivation questionnaire (Baron et al., 2022) to address "Energy level" (b1300) and "Motivation" (b1301) can be considered. Providing detailed suggestions are beyond the scope of this study.

5 Conclusion

Current hearing assessment methodologies often fail to address all aspects related to the causes and consequences of hearing loss. To bridge this gap, a novel highly ecologically valid dataset, consisting of the results from a variety of audiological perceptual measurements, was generated. To determine the extent to which this database represents hearing loss in daily life, the measurements and their outcomes were linked to the ICF categories of core sets for hearing loss. The findings showed that applying all these measures addressed 92.5% of the ICF categories in the brief core set and 50.4% in the comprehensive core set for hearing loss. This indicates that combining these measures enables a more comprehensive, patient-centred assessment of hearing loss and provides a holistic data that can be integrated into models of speech intelligibility and listening effort. Such an approach supports the development of more effective hearing aids, ultimately improving user satisfaction, functionality, and overall quality of life.

Ethics statement

The studies involving humans were approved by the "Research Ethics Committee of the Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg", in German: "Kommission für Forschungsfolgenabschätzung und Ethik der Carl von Ossietzky Universität" (Drs.EK/2021/031, Drs.EK/2021/031-02, Drs.EK/2021/031-03, Drs.EK/2021/031-04).

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

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Table 1: Linking of dataset measurements to the WHO International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) Core Sets for Hearing Loss. The table shows each ICF category code, its inclusion in the Brief (CSHL-B) and Comprehensive (CSHL-C) Core Sets for Hearing Loss, and the corresponding measurements that address it. Where applicable, measurements were linked to detailed subcategories. HCT: HEAR-COMMAND Tool, ACALES: Adaptive Categorical Listening Effort Scaling, GÖSA: Göttinger Sentence test, PTA: Pure-tone Audiometry, TIN: Tone IN Noise detection, LVM: Loudness Validation Method, OLSA: Oldenburger Sentence test, CCOLSA: Concurrent Oldenburger Sentence test, Coupler: Coupler measurements, in-situ: in-situ recordings, DIAPIX: Dialogue Picture Task, ACALOS: Binaural Broadband Loudness Scaling via Adaptive Categorical Loudness Scaling measurement.

CODE	ICF category	CSHL - B	CSHL - C	Subcategories	Measurements
Body Functions					
b126	Temperament and personality functions	×	×		HCT
b134	Sleep Functions	-	-		HCT
b140	Attention functions	×	×		HCT
				Sustaining attention (b1400) Shifting attention (b1401)	DIAPIX, CCOLSA, ACALES, GÖSA, OLSA, TIN, LVM, PTA, ACALOS
				Dividing attention (b1402)	DIAPIX, CCOLSA, ACALES, GÖSA, OLSA, TIN
				Sharing attention (b1403)	DIAPIX
b144	Memory functions	×	×		HCT
				Short-term memory (b1440)	DIAPIX, CCOLSA, GÖSA, OLSA
b152	Emotional functions	×	×		HCT
b1560	Auditory perception	-	×		HCT, DIAPIX, CCOLSA, ACALES, GÖSA, OLSA, TIN, LVM, PTA, ACALOS
b1561	Visual perception	-	×		DIAPIX
b164	Higher-level cognitive functions	-	×	Problem-solving (b1646)	DIAPIX, CCOLSA
b167	Mental functions of language	-	×		HCT
				Reception of spoken language (b16700) [Reception of language (b1670)]	DIAPIX
				Expression of spoken language (b16710) [Expression of language (b1671)]	
b210	Seeing functions	×	×		HCT
				Light sensitivity (b21020)	DIAPIX
				Colour vision (b21021)	
				Contrast sensitivity (b21022) [Quality of vision (b2102)]	
b2300	Sound detection	×	×		HCT, DIAPIX, CCOLSA, ACALES, GÖSA, OLSA, TIN, LVM, PTA, ACALOS
b2301	Sound discrimination	×	×		HCT, TIN
b2302	Localization of sound source	×	×		HCT, DIAPIX, CCOLSA, ACALES, GÖSA, OLSA
b2303	Lateralization of sound source	×	-		HCT, DIAPIX, CCOLSA, ACALES, GÖSA, OLSA
b2304	Speech discrimination	×	×		HCT, DIAPIX, CCOLSA, ACALES, GÖSA, OLSA
b240	Sensations associated with hearing and vestibular functions	×	×		HCT
b250	Taste function	-	-		HCT
b255	Smell function	-	-		HCT
b280	Sensation of pain	-	×		HCT
b310	Voice functions	-	×		HCT
b320	Articulation functions			Production of voice (b3100)	DIAPIX, CCOLSA, GÖSA, OLSA

				Quality of voice (b3101)	
b320	Articulation functions	-	×		HCT, DIAPIX, CCOLSA, GÖSA, OLSA
b330	Fluency and rhythm of speech functions	-	×		HCT
				Fluency of speech (b3300)	HCT, DIAPIX, CCOLSA, GÖSA, OLSA
				Rhythm of speech (b3301)	
				Speed of speech (b3302)	
Melody of speech (b3303)					
Body Structures					
s240	Structure of external ear	×	×		Otoscopy
s250	Structure of Middle ear	×	×		Otoscopy
ACTIVITIES AND PARTICIPATION					
d110	Watching	-	×		HCT, DIAPIX
d115	Listening	×	×		HCT, DIAPIX, CCOLSA, ACALES, GÖSA, OLSA, TIN, LVM, PTA, ACALOS
d155	Acquiring skills	-	×	Acquiring complex skills (d1551)	DIAPIX, CCOLSA
d160	Focusing attention	-	×		HCT
				Focusing attention on the person (d1600)	DIAPIX
				Focusing attention on the environment (d1601)	DIAPIX, CCOLSA, ACALES, GÖSA, OLSA, TIN, LVM, PTA, ACALOS
d175	Solving problems	-	×	Solving complex problems (d1751)	DIAPIX, CCOLSA
d220	Undertaking multiple tasks	-	×		HCT
				Completing multiple tasks (d2201)	DIAPIX, CCOLSA
d240	Handling stress and other psychological demands	×	×		HCT
				Handling responsibilities (d2400)	DIAPIX, CCOLSA
d310	Communicating with receiving spoken messages	×	×		HCT
				Communicating with - receiving - simple spoken messages (d3100)	DIAPIX
d330	Speaking	-	×		HCT
				Producing meaningful sounds (d3300)	CCOLSA
				Producing complex spoken messages (d3302)	DIAPIX
d350	Conversation	×	×	Starting a conversation (d3500)	HCT, DIAPIX, CCOLSA
				Sustaining a conversation (d3501)	
				Ending a conversation (d3502)	
				Conversing with one person (d3503)	HCT, DIAPIX,
Conversing with many people (d3504)	HCT, CCOLSA				
d355	Discussion	-	×		HCT
				Discussion with one person (d3550)	DIAPIX
d360	Using communication devices and techniques	×	×		HCT

d710	Basic interpersonal interactions	-	×		HCT
d720	Complex interpersonal interactions	-	×		HCT
d730	Relating with strangers	-	×		HCT, DIAPIX
d740	Formal relationships	-	×		HCT
d750	Informal social relationships	-	×		HCT
d760	Family relationships	×	×		HCT
d820	School education	×	×		HCT
d830	Higher education	-	×		HCT
d850	Remunerative employment	×	×		HCT
d855	Non-remunerative employment	-	×		HCT
d910	Community life	×	×		HCT
d920	Recreation and leisure	-	×		HCT
ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS					
e125	Products and technology for communication	×	×		HCT
				Assistive products and technology for communication (e1251)	in-situ, Coupler
e150	Design, construction and building products and technology of buildings for public use	-	×		HCT, CCOLSA, OLSA, ACALES, DIAPIX
e155	Design, construction and building products and technology of buildings for private use	-	×		OLSA, ACALES
e240	Light	-	×		HCT, DIAPIX
e250	Sound	×	×	Sound Intensity (e2500)	HCT, DIAPIX, CCOLSA, ACALES, GÖSA, OLSA, TIN, LVM, PTA, ACALOS, in-situ, Coupler
				Sound Quality (e2501)	HCT, DIAPIX, CCOLSA, ACALES, GÖSA, OLSA, TIN, in-situ, Coupler
e310	Immediate family	×	×		HCT
e320	Friends	-	×		HCT
e355	Health professionals	×	×		HCT
e410	Individual attitudes of immediate family members	×	×		HCT

e420	Individual attitude of friends	-	×		HCT
e460	Societal attitudes	×	×		HCT
e535	Communication services, systems and policies	-	×		HCT
e580	Health services, systems and policies	×	×		HCT

Table 2 Number of categories in each ICF domain and percentage of overall categories of Core Set for Hearing Loss addressed by each methodology. BF: Body Functions, BS: Body Structures AP: Activities and Participation, EF: Environmental Factors. The total number of categories in each domain given after the domain abbreviation. Example: EN (7): Originally, there are 7 categories in EF domain. HCT: HEAR-COMMAND Tool, ACALES: Adaptive Categorical Listening Effort Scaling, GÖSA: Göttinger Sentence test, PTA: Pure-tone Audiometry, TIN: Tone IN Noise detection, LVM: Loudness Validation Method, OLSA: Oldenburger Sentence test, CCOLSA: Concurrent Oldenburger Sentence test, Coupler: Coupler measurements, in-situ: in-situ recordings, DIAPIX: Dialogue Picture Task, ACALOS: Binaural Broadband Loudness Scaling via Adaptive Categorical Loudness Scaling measurement.

MEASUREMENT	BRIEF CORE SET FOR HEARING LOSS						COMPREHENSIVE CORE SET FOR HEARING LOSS					
	BF (7)	BS (4)	AP (9)	EN (7)	Overall (27)	Overall (%)	BF (22)	BS (5)	AP (42)	EN (48)	Overall (117)	Overall (%)
HCT	7	0	9	7	23	85.1	16	0	23	13	52	44.4
OTOSCOPY	0	2	0	0	2	7.4	0	2	0	0	2	1.7
PTA	2	0	1	1	4	14.8	3	0	2	1	6	5.1
ACALOS	2	0	1	1	4	14.8	3	0	2	1	6	5.1
LVM	2	0	1	1	4	14.8	3	0	2	1	6	5.1
TIN	2	0	1	1	4	14.8	4	0	2	2	8	6.8
GÖSA	3	0	1	1	5	18.5	9	0	2	2	13	11.1
OLSA	3	0	1	1	5	18.5	9	0	2	4	15	12.8
ACALES	3	0	1	1	5	18.5	9	0	2	4	15	12.8
DIAPIX	4	0	4	1	9	33.3	13	0	12	4	29	24.7
CCOLSA	3	0	2	1	6	22.2	11	0	8	4	25	21.3
IN-SITU	0	0	0	2	2	7.4	0	0	0	3	3	2.5
COUPLER	0	0	0	2	2	7.4	0	0	0	3	3	2.5
ALL	7	2	9	7	25	92.5	18	2	25	14	59	50.4

Table 3 This table presents the comprehensive ICF Core Set for Hearing Loss categories not addressed in the dataset, organized into seven conceptual groups. Groups 1 to 4 combine Activities and Participation and Environmental Factors categories. Group 1: broad general-life dimensions. Group 2: specific concepts. Group 3: mobility and transportation. Group 4: education, vocational training, skill development, and learning activities. Group 5: individual's interaction with people in wider social networks. Group 6: missing Body Functions categories. Group 7: missing Body Structures.

ICF Category		Group	ICF Category		Group
BODY FUNCTIONS			ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS		
b117	Intellectual functions	6	e140	Products and technology for culture, recreation and sport	1

b1300	Energy level	6	e145	Products and technology for the practice of religion and spirituality	1
b1301	Motivation	6	e225	Climate	1
b235	Vestibular functions	6	e315	Extended family	5
BODY STRUCTURES			e325	Acquaintances, peers, colleagues, neighbours and community members	5
s110	Structure of brain	7	e330	People in position of authority	5
s260	Structure of inner ear	7	e335	People in subordinate positions	5
s710	Structure of head and neck region	7	e340	Personal care providers and personal assistants	5
ACTIVITIES AND PARTICIPATION			e345	Strangers	5
d140	Learning to read	4	e350	Domesticated animals	2
d315	Communicating with - receiving - nonverbal messages	2	e360	Other professionals	5
d440	Fine hand use	3	e415	Individual attitudes of extended family members	5
d470	Using transportation	3	e425	Individual attitudes of acquaintances, peers, colleagues, neighbours and community members	5
d475	Driving	3	e430	Individual attitudes of people in position of authority	5
d620	Acquisition of goods and services	1	e440	Individual attitudes of personal care providers and personal assistants	5
d660	Assisting others	1	e445	Individual attitudes of strangers	5
d770	Intimate relationships	2	e450	Individual attitudes of health professionals	5
d810	Informal training	4	e455	Individual attitude of other professionals	5
d825	Vocational training	4	e465	Social norms, practices and ideologies	1
d840	Apprenticeship (work preparation)	4	e515	Architecture and construction services, systems and policies	1
d845	Acquiring, keeping and terminating a job	4	e525	Housing services, systems and policies	1
d860	Basic economic transactions	1	e540	Transportation services, systems and policies	1
d870	Economic self-sufficiency	1	e545	Civil protection services, systems and policies	1
d930	Religion and spirituality	1	e550	Legal services, systems and policies	1
d940	Human rights	1	e555	Associations and organizational services, systems and policies	1
d950	Political life and citizenship	1	e560	Media services, systems and policies	1
ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS			e570	Social security services, systems and policies	1
e115	Products and technology for personal use in daily living	2	e575	General social support services, systems and policies	1
e120	Products and technology for personal indoor and outdoor mobility and transportation	3	e585	Education and training services, systems and policies	1
e130	Products and technology for education	4	e590	Labour and employment services, systems and policies	1
e135	Products and technology for employment	4			